

Mechanism: The parent species of V^V in mineral acids is considered⁴ to be VO_2^+ . At slightly higher acid concentration VO_2^+ is assumed to be in equilibrium with $V(OH)_2^{2+}$ (equation 1)

The marked colour of sulphuric acid solution of V^V suggests that one HSO_4^- may be incorporated in the active species⁵⁻⁷ which may be represented as $V(OH)_2HSO_4^+$ (equation 2). The effect of the addition of $NaHSO_4$ and Na_2SO_4 lends support to the equilibrium,

Polymerisation test with acrylonitrile is positive, indicating the formation of free radical intermediates and also that V^V acts as one-electron oxidant.

The experimental results, therefore, lead to the following rate expression.

At constant $[V^V]_T$

$$k_{obs} = \frac{K_1' K_2 k_1 [\text{ketone}] [H_2SO_4]}{1 + K_1' [H_2SO_4] + K_1' K_2 [\text{ketone}] [H_2SO_4]} \quad (7)$$

According to Wells and Kuritsyn⁸, the equilibrium constant for the formation of $V(OH)_2^{2+}$ is much less than one. Therefore, it can be assumed that K_1' is very small as compared to $K_2 k_1$.

$$\frac{1}{k_{obs}} = \frac{1}{X [\text{ketone}]} + \frac{1}{k_1} \quad (8)$$

where $X = K_1' K_2 k_1 [H_2SO_4]$ at constant concentration of H_2SO_4 . The plots of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[\text{ketone}]$ are linear with positive intercept on Y-axis.

Since K_1' is less than unity, $[K_1' K_2]$ is also less than one and hence, the equation (7) may be expressed as

$$k_{obs} = k_1 K_1' K_2 [\text{ketone}] [H_2SO_4] \quad (9)$$

and at constant concentration of sulphuric acid

$$k_{obs} = K' [\text{ketone}]$$

where, $K' = K_1' K_2 k_1 [H_2SO_4]$.

The plots of k_{obs} vs $[\text{ketone}]$ should be linear passing through the origin.

Values of entropy of activation too confirm the C-H fission in the mechanistic steps. Kinetic results show that the reactivity of benzoyl acetone is more

than acetyl acetone. This may be due to the conjugation effect.

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Kinetics of Oxidation of Diphenyl Methane by Selenium Dioxide

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SELENIUM dioxide has been used as an oxidant in the study of kinetics of oxidation of some ketones¹⁻⁴, though similar studies with diphenylmethane have not been made so far. The rate of oxidation of diphenyl methane by chromic acid in glacial acetic acid is extremely rapid at first, but soon slackens and stops almost entirely after a few hours though both diphenylmethane and Cr^{VI} remain in solution⁵. Literature survey shows that much work has been done on the mechanism of oxidation of olefins by selenium dioxide⁶⁻¹², but it seems that no attention has been given to the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of diphenylmethane and related hydrocarbons by selenium dioxide. These have prompted us to study the kinetics of oxidation of diphenylmethane by selenium dioxide to obtain the information on the mechanism of oxidation.

In continuation of our recent interest in the kinetics of oxidation of organic compounds containing active methylene group by selenium dioxide¹³⁻¹⁴, we report, in this note, the kinetics of oxidation of diphenylmethane by selenium

dioxide in 80% (v/v) dioxane-water mixture in the presence of perchloric acid (0.30-0.75M).

Experimental

Reagents used were selenium dioxide (Loba), diphenylmethane (Sisco), dioxane (B.D.H.), perchloric acid (Riedel), and the other chemicals were of A.R. quality. Stock solution of selenium dioxide was prepared in distilled water and standardised iodometrically. The reactions were studied in thermostat ($\pm 0.1^\circ$). The rate of reaction was determined by estimating the unreacted selenium dioxide iodometrically⁴.

Stoichiometry of the reaction was determined. It was found that one mole of diphenylmethane for complete oxidation required one mole of selenium dioxide.

The product, benzophenone, was identified by preparing 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 237°. Selenium was tested by its characteristic spot test¹⁵.

Results and Discussion

The kinetics of oxidation of diphenylmethane by selenium dioxide has been studied in 80% (v/v) dioxane-water mixture in the presence of perchloric acid. The order of reaction with respect to selenium dioxide is one. The pseudo first order rate constant increases with increase in the concentration of diphenylmethane, however, the value of $k/[DPM]$ remains constant. This clearly indicates that the order with respect to diphenylmethane is unity. The pseudo first order rate constant increases with increase in the concentration of perchloric acid, but the dependence of rate constant on perchloric acid concentration is not simple (Table 1).

The pseudo first order rate constant in selenium dioxide increases with the decrease in selenium dioxide concentration. It is known¹⁶⁻¹⁷ that selenium(IV) dimerises in aqueous acidic media, so, selenium(IV) will exist both in monomeric and dimeric form in the reaction mixture in the concentration range¹⁸ employed for the present investigation. Thus, the increase in the rate with decreasing concentration of selenium dioxide may be attributed to lower concentration of dimeric selenium(IV), that is, by assuming that as an oxidant the dimer is less reactive than the monomer as in the case of cerium(IV).

The change in ionic strength produced by K_2SO_4 has nearly no effect on the reaction rate, suggesting that at least one of the reacting species involved in the rate determining step is a neutral molecule¹⁹. The increase in the percentage of dioxane in the reaction mixture largely enhances the reaction rate (Table 1). The plot of $\log k$ vs percentage composition of dioxane, that is, $1/D$ is linear having positive slope, suggesting the reaction is a positive ion-dipole²⁰ type.

The kinetics of oxidation of diphenylmethane by selenium dioxide has been studied at four different temperatures. The plot of $\log k$ vs $1/T$ is linear. The activation parameters have been evaluated, using Arrhenius and Eyring's equations. The calculated values of energy of activation (E_a), frequency factor (A), entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) and free energy of activation (ΔG^\ddagger) are 15.65 kcal mol^{-1} , 1.51×10^6 $l\ mol^{-1}\ sec^{-1}$, -35.10 e.u. and 25.95 kcal mol^{-1} , respectively.

Mechanism: Based on the above experimental facts, the proposed reaction mechanism involves an attack of conjugated acid of selenious acid, $H_2SeO_3^+$, at the active methylene group of diphenylmethane (I) in a slow step to give selenium(II) intermediate (II). The latter would yield benzophenone by 1,2-elimination of H_2SeO , which ultimately gives Se and H_2O .

TABLE I.—EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION OF REACTANTS AND SOLVENT COMPOSITION ON REACTION RATE

Temp. = 65°		Dioxane-water = 4 : 1(v/v)			
Effect of selenium dioxide concentration					
[Diphenylmethane] = 0.5M,	[HClO ₄] = 0.5M				
[SeO ₂]M	0.005	0.010	0.015	0.020	
10 ⁴ k min ⁻¹	1.56	1.49	1.47	1.42	
Effect of diphenylmethane concentration					
[Selenium dioxide] = 0.01M,	[HClO ₄] = 0.5M				
[DPM]M	0.25	0.30	0.40	0.50	0.60
10 ⁴ k min ⁻¹	0.76	0.89	1.18	1.49	1.82
10 ⁴ k/[DPM]	3.04	2.96	2.95	2.98	3.03
1 mol ⁻¹ min ⁻¹					
Effect of perchloric acid concentration					
[Selenium dioxide] = 0.01M,	[Diphenylmethane] = 0.5M				
[HClO ₄]M	0.30	0.40	0.50	0.60	0.75
10 ⁴ k min ⁻¹	0.93	1.17	1.49	2.14	2.75
Effect of percentage composition of dioxane					
[Selenium dioxide] = 0.01M,	[Diphenylmethane] = 0.5M,				
[HClO ₄] = 0.5M					
Dioxane-water (v/v)	75-25	80-20	85-15		
10 ⁴ k min ⁻¹	0.73	1.49	3.38		
(k = k ₁ /2.303)					

In the present kinetic investigation, it has been observed that under identical experimental conditions, the acid catalysed oxidation of diphenylmethane by selenium dioxide occurs at a measurable

tate in dioxane-water (Table 2), while the oxidation rate, being very slow, is not measurable in acetic acid-water. This indicates that acetic acid is not a good solvent in the selenium dioxide oxidation of diphenylmethane. However, acetic acid has been found to be a good solvent in the selenium dioxide oxidation of olefins⁶⁻¹³, ketones^{1-4,9}, ester¹⁴, etc.

Unlike chromic acid⁵ oxidation of diphenylmethane in glacial acetic acid, the acid catalysed oxidation of diphenylmethane by selenium dioxide in dioxane-water, under the condition $[\text{SeO}_2] \ll [\text{diphenylmethane}]$, proceeds smoothly till the oxidant is consumed completely (Table 2).

TABLE 2—ACID CATALYSED OXIDATION OF DIPHENYLMETHANE BY SELENIUM DIOXIDE UNDER CONDITION $[\text{SeO}_2] \ll [\text{DPM}]$ IN 80%(v/v) DIOXANE-WATER

[SeO ₂] = 0.01M, [DPM] = 0.5M, [HClO ₄] = 0.75M, Temp. = 65°						
Time min.	0	30	60	90	120	150
[SeO ₂] in ml of	4.1	3.5	3.0	2.6	2.2	1.8
Na ₂ S ₂ O ₈	1.4	1.1	0.9	0.75	0.6	0.5
10 ³ k min ⁻¹	—	2.29	2.26	2.22	2.25	2.38
(k = k ₁ /2.303)	2.59	2.75	2.74	2.75	2.78	2.76

The temperature coefficient for the present reaction is nearly 2, while relatively small effect of temperature was observed⁵ in the chromic acid oxidation of diphenylmethane.

The present kinetic investigation gives information on the mechanism of acid catalysed oxidation of diphenylmethane by selenium dioxide, which has not been reported previously.

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Studies on Resorcinol Formaldehyde Cationic Resins†

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SYNTHESIS and study of ion exchangers is of interest because of their large scale use particularly in analytical chemistry and in the softening of water. There is a greater need now either to find out altogether newer resins which are economical compared to the existing exchangers or to identify substitutes which can partly replace the polymeric content of the existing exchangers to a considerable extent while retaining the properties of the parent resins.

Earlier work done has revealed that coke¹, sawdust², lignite could be substituted upto 30-40 percent in phenolic cationities. Such a substitution did not have any adverse effect and in addition the composites obtained were macroporous.

In fact, cation exchangers can be made from almost any material which reacts with sulphuric acid without being dissolved, such as the sulphonated olive pits³, and nut shells and spent coffee⁴, tar⁵, paper⁶, cotton, etc.

The present work is an attempt to prepare and study the properties of sulphonated resorcinol formaldehyde cation exchangers substituted partially by sulphonated charcoal obtained from coconut fibre.

Experimental

Preparation of the sample: Reagents used were resorcinol and formaldehyde (B.D.H.), and concentrated H₂SO₄ (sp.gr.1.82). Coconut fibre was procured from local industries and cleaned before use.

Resorcinol (10 g) and conc. H₂SO₄ (12.5 ml) were mixed slowly with constant cooling. Then the

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